

CHARACTERIZING EFFECTS OF SPACE WEATHERING ON APOLLO ROCK SAMPLES USING SPECTROSCOPIC TECHNIQUES TO AID LUNAR EXPLORATION MISSIONS. D. Das¹, E. Cloutis¹, D. Applin¹, K. Peters¹, C. Tai Udovicic¹, A. Cunje¹, H. Vannier¹, T. Ledoux¹, and S. C. Lambert¹. Centre for Terrestrial and Planetary Exploration, University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Avenue, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada R3B 2E9; d.das-ra@uwinnipeg.ca.

Introduction: Space weathering describes the various processes that affect the spectral and compositional properties of the lunar surface due to exposure to the space environment [1,2]. Some of the space weathering processes include micrometeorite impacts, and irradiation by solar wind and cosmic rays. These processes cause chemical and physical changes to the lunar surface and are collectively known as maturation—a surface is more mature if it has experienced higher levels of space weathering [1]. Space weathering-induced maturity changes affect the way that light is absorbed, reflected, and emitted by mature surfaces on the Moon and other airless bodies [1,2]. One major effect is the progressive darkening and reddening of the lunar surface in the VIS/NIR/SWIR spectral range due primarily to the production of nanophase iron particles [1,3,4]. However, the effects are dependent on the grain size and composition of the target material [4,5]. Maturity studies of the lunar surface are essential for understanding the Moon's geological history, enabling safe landings, and identifying resources for future exploration [6].

In support of planned Canadian lunar exploration missions, the Center for Terrestrial and Planetary Exploration (C-TAPE) at the University of Winnipeg has been spectrally characterizing three Apollo rock samples that were recently acquired from the NASA Johnson Space Center (JSC) to perform non-destructive spectral analysis. Here we present preliminary spectral data on Apollo 16 sample 65015. The overall results of this work are anticipated to improve analysis and interpretation of lunar observation made using Earth based, orbiter and landed missions data.

Methods: The samples consist of three types of lunar rocks: an olivine basalt, impact melt breccia, and an ilmenite basalt: sample numbers 15555, 65015, and 71175, respectively. Sample 15555 is an Apollo 15 mare basalt from the Hadley Rille area [7] and most closely resemble in composition the Apollo 12 olivine-rich basalts [8]. Sample 65016 is an Apollo 16 KREEP-basalt type [9, 10] and sample 71175 is an Apollo 17 equigranular ilmenite basalt [11, 12, 13]. We have received both upper and lower surface chips of these rocks such that we can compare the exposed space weathered upper surfaces to the pristine lower surfaces of each. The exposed surface of the buried parent rocks shows large amount of pitting and the buried areas do not (inferred based on images of parent

rock photographs). We have spectrally characterized these samples using non-destructive multispectral techniques including reflectance spectroscopy. For each sample, the upper and lower surface counterparts have been analyzed using the SpecIM IQ hyperspectral imager (400-1000nm, 7 nm resolution) to acquire hyperspectral reflectance images. These samples have also been analyzed by reflectance spectroscopy using the Analytical Spectral Device (LabSpec 4 Hi-Res:350-2500 nm 3-6 nm resolution) to acquire data in the VIS/NIR/SWIR range.

Table 1. Apollo samples to study space weathering (exterior & interior surfaces of the parent rock).

Sample	Fraction ID	Weight (g)	Mission	Characterization
15555	859, 47	2.045	Apollo 15	Mare basalt [6]
15555	465, 58	47.3	Apollo 15	Mare basalt [6]
15555	1117, 467	1.4	Apollo 15	Mare basalt [6]
65015	15, 0 (Stock)	41.8	Apollo 16	KREEP basalt [9, 10]
65015	323, 15	1.4	Apollo 16	KREEP basalt [9, 10]
65015	25, 0	1314.3	Apollo 16	KREEP basalt [9, 10]
65015	326, 25 (Buried)	1.6	Apollo 16	KREEP basalt [9, 10]
71175	0, 0	114.2	Apollo 17	Ilmenite basalt [11, 12]
71175	48, 0 (Top)	1.48	Apollo 17	Ilmenite basalt [11, 12, 13]
71175	0, 0	114.2	Apollo 17	Ilmenite basalt [11, 12, 13]
71175	50, 0 (Bottom)	0.849	Apollo 17	Ilmenite basalt [11, 12, 13]

Preliminary Results: Here we present the preliminary reflectance data acquired on samples 65105 (326, 25 Buried) and 65105 (323, 15). The approximate diameter of reflectance analysis is 6.7 mm and is shown in **Fig. 1**.

The reflectance spectra shown in **Fig. 2** indicates that the 65015.366 buried sample has a much bluer spectral slope over the entire VNIR spectral range. The band I and band II centers for 65015.323, 15 and 65105.326, 25 are nearly identical at 934 nm/1933 nm and 936 nm/1925, respectively. The band I FWHM are 229 nm and 232 nm, while the band I/band II band-area-ratios are 1.87 and 1.93, respectively. Given that the band parameters indicate a very similar composition, this may indicate that the spectral properties of the rock were preserved when buried, thus indicating a lack of space weathering.

Figure 1. Area of reflectance analysis on Apollo 16 samples a) 65105 (326, 25 Buried) and b) 65105 (323, 15). Tick marks are 1 mm intervals.

Figure 2. Preliminary reflectance data Apollo 16 samples 65105 (326, 25 Buried): Black and 65105 (323, 15): Red

Future work: The data acquired from the upper and lower surfaces of the three samples will be compared to characterize variations in space weathering for the exposed and shielded surfaces of the rock. We will derive Optical Maturity and FeO wt.% maps over the surfaces of these rocks. This data will also be compared to the comprehensive spectral library of lunar regolith and meteorite samples at C-TAPE for characterization of patina compositional variation in the three Apollo JSC samples. The results of this work will inform ongoing efforts to produce next-generation orbital and rover-based lunar instrumentation for characterizing lunar space weathering and in-situ geochemical analyses.

Summary: Reflectance spectroscopy is a widely used technique to explore the surface composition of the Moon and the results of this work will be directly comparable to Earth-based lunar observations [14], lunar orbiter data [15], and landed mission data [16]. This work will add to the library of spectral reflectance properties of Apollo samples and act as a guide to assessing the spectral qualities of lunar simulants.

References:

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Acknowledgements: This study was supported by the Canadian Space Agency (CW2421931; 9F057-240377) and the European Space Agency (4000xxxxxx/25/NL/AS). We thank the NASA Astromaterials Program for providing these samples.